

A Review of *Histoplasma capsulatum* Associated with Pulmonary Histoplasmosis

Najwan Abbas Mohammed ✉

Biotechnology Department, College of Science, University of Diyala, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Mohammed, N.A. (2024). A Review of *Histoplasma capsulatum* Associated with Pulmonary Histoplasmosis. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 335-346.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).35](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).35)

Abstract:

Histoplasma capsulatum is an intracellular dimorphic fungus that is distributed across the globe and is responsible for pulmonary histoplasmosis. Bats and birds are natural reservoirs for this pathogen, which is found in soils contaminated with these animals' excreta, grows in nature as a mold, and grows in the tissues of a susceptible host as a yeast. Transmission of the fungus occurs through inhalation of airborne spores. The clinical manifestation of primary pulmonary histoplasmosis, which is prevalent in some regions of North America, typically includes nonspecific symptoms

like "fevers, malaise, chills, cough, weight loss, and wheezing." Importantly, the amount of fungal particles breathed and the host's immune status determine the severity of this fungal infection, with higher morbidity and mortality rates among immunocompromised individuals.

Pulmonary histoplasmosis is usually an acute, chronic, or disseminated infection and, like the primary form, resolves spontaneously or with antifungal therapy in immunocompetent hosts. Most pulmonary infections in immunocompetent hosts are asymptomatic, with acute pulmonary infections occurring after prolonged exposure to large quantities of spores. Conversely, in individuals with weakened immune systems, histoplasmosis frequently manifests as a disseminated illness, typically with a high mortality rate in untreated cases. Nevertheless, adequate therapy can significantly reduce the mortality rate.

The aim of this review was to emphasize the key aspects of *H. capsulatum* associated with pulmonary histoplasmosis, including geographic distribution of *H. capsulatum*, clinical presentation of pulmonary histoplasmosis, pathogenesis, immune response and virulence factors of *H. capsulatum*, pathophysiology of pulmonary histoplasmosis and COVID-19, diagnostic approaches, and treatment strategies.

Keywords: yeast, *Histoplasma capsulatum*, Histoplasmosis, COVID-19.

Introduction

Histoplasma capsulatum is a fungus that exhibits dimorphism and grows as a yeast at 37 °C. The yeast develops as small (< 2 µm in diameter), uninucleate, round to egg-shaped cells that reproduce by budding and were recovered either intracellular in a macrophage, or else extracellular. The mold replicates by conidiophores producing microconidia and

large, thick-walled macroconidia, which are its infectious form outside the host (Brilhante et al. 2023). The microconidia and small hyphal fragments of *H. capsulatum* are light enough to be suspended in the air for prolonged periods and thus entrapment within an area with a high density of these spores leads to the infection. In a laboratory setting with room temperature, *Histoplasma* forms aerial hyphae that eventually give rise to microconidia, the predominant form

within the young mycelium. Various stimuli have been shown to facilitate the conversion of the mold form into the yeast phase (Bagal et al. 2023). *H. capsulatum*, the causative agent of histoplasmosis, has a worldwide geographic distribution but is mainly reported in regions of the world where its thermo-tolerance enables survival in organic matter (guano, ant droppings, litter) in soil or within bat and bird roosts at appropriate levels of heat and humidity in tropical and subtropical climates (Taylor et al. 2022). Pulmonary histoplasmosis caused by *H. capsulatum* is a lung infection associated with exposure to spores found in soil that has been contaminated with bird or bat excrement. This particular infection is not contagious and occurs when individuals inhale spores or mixed mycelial spore forms from disturbed contaminated habitats (Souza et al. 2023). Initially, the infection may not show any signs or just have minor symptoms similar to those of the flu, making it challenging to diagnose. However, in susceptible individuals, such as those who already have respiratory disorders or compromised immune systems, the infection may progress to severe pulmonary histoplasmosis (Sayeed et al. 2022). The clinical presentation of pulmonary histoplasmosis can vary from mild to severe manifestations. "Chest pain, persistent cough, fatigue, shortness of breath, weight loss, and night sweats" are typical symptoms. Chest radiographs may reveal infiltrates in the lungs, hilar lymphadenopathy, or cavities resembling tuberculosis. Definitive diagnosis often relies on laboratory methods, including respiratory specimen cultures, serological tests, and molecular techniques (Chen et al. 2024).

Geographic Distribution of *Histoplasma capsulatum*

Histoplasma capsulatum var. *capsulatum* and *Histoplasma capsulatum* var. *duboisii* are the two distinct organisms responsible for human histoplasmosis, the former has been found on every continent with the exception of Antarctica. Pulmonary histoplasmosis exhibits geographical variability. The middle and eastern United States,

along the Ohio and Mississippi Rivers, are the locations in North America with the highest endemicity (Barros et al. 2023). The Ohio and Mississippi river valleys in the United States, as well as Central and South America, Africa, the Indian subcontinent, and Southeast Asia, are home to *H. capsulatum* var. *capsulatum*. The geographic range of *H. capsulatum* var. *duboisii* includes Central and West Africa. *H. capsulatum* grow well in the temperature and soil of the United States when there is a large concentration of bird or bat droppings. Conversely, it was believed that the habitat of *H. capsulatum* in non-shaded soil was limited to soil that had a large proportion of droppings (Bagal et al. 2023).

H. capsulatum was discovered in soil samples from a coffee plantation in Colombia that were 26 °C and free of bird and bat droppings. The geographic range and environmental presence of *H. capsulatum* var. *duboisii* are still unclear. With the exception of Africa, the majority of individuals are affected by *H. capsulatum* var. *capsulatum* in urban areas and *H. capsulatum* var. *duboisii* in rural areas. Soil and climate variables are also changeable. Soil produces infectious arthroconidia, which are probably affected by several factors such as temperature, humidity, nutrition, and the existence of bat or bird guano. When considered collectively, the environmental elements that affect the growth of *H. capsulatum* are probably also responsible for its dispersion. Different migration patterns of humans in tourist regions and wild birds in the environment may cause changes in the distribution of *H. capsulatum* (Lockhart et al. 2021).

Clinical Presentation of Pulmonary Histoplasmosis

Pulmonary histoplasmosis can manifest in various clinical presentations, ranging from acute to chronic and disseminated forms. Clinical manifestations may include symptoms such as "fevers, coughs, chills, malaise, wheezing, and weight loss", although the majority of affected individuals may display no apparent symptoms, leading to potential misdiagnosis as other pulmonary diseases such as tuberculosis (Zhu et al. 20216). A large

asurable section of population exposure to histoplasmosis may be widespread in highly endemic areas, with a significant percentage developing symptoms following high-inoculum exposure, typically presenting as "flu-like symptoms such as headache, fever, dry cough, malaise, and chest discomfort." (Barros et al. 2023). In acute cases, interstitial infiltrates or diffuse patchy opacities are frequently seen on chest imaging, potentially connected with mediastinal and hilar adenopathy. Early recognition of these clinical presentations is crucial for timely diagnosis and management of pulmonary histoplasmosis (Sun et al. 2020). There are three types of pulmonary histoplasmosis that might show clinical symptoms: acute, chronic, and disseminated. Other types of illnesses may also arise (Wheat et al. 2016).

Acute Pulmonary Histoplasmosis

Acute pulmonary histoplasmosis is a form of primary pulmonary histoplasmosis caused by the dimorphic fungus *H. capsulatum*. The severity of this fungal infection is contingent upon the

quantity of fungal particles breathed and the immunological condition of the person (Zhu et al. 2016). Common clinical manifestations could involve symptoms such as "fevers, cough, malaise chills, weight loss, and wheezing," with some persons who are infected may not show any noticeable symptoms, which can result in misdiagnosis as other lung diseases, such as tuberculosis (Barros et al. 2023).

Chest imaging commonly shows scattered areas of cloudiness or infiltrations across tissues, and in cases of mild to moderate severity [Figure 1], therapy is generally not required. However, individuals experiencing symptoms lasting longer than 1 month should be administered Itraconazole. The recommended treatment for people with moderately severe to severe acute pulmonary histoplasmosis is Lipid Amphotericin B followed by itraconazole. For early detection and effective treatment, it is essential to comprehend a distinctive presentation of acute pulmonary histoplasmosis (Sun et al. 2020).

Figure 1. A case Series of Immunocompetent Individuals Suffering with Acute Pulmonary Histoplasmosis from Guadeloupe, Martinique, and French Guiana

Chronic Pulmonary Histoplasmosis

Chronic pulmonary histoplasmosis is a specific type of infection that is defined by a long-lasting clinical course. Chronic pulmonary histoplasmosis is characterized by less severe and long-lasting symptoms that may be similar to those of other lung illnesses, such as tuberculosis (Zhu et al. 2016). Individuals suffering with chronic pulmonary histoplasmosis may exhibit persistent symptoms such as a long-lasting, mild cough, fever, and gradual reduction in body weight. Furthermore, before histoplasmosis manifests, people are often misidentified with bacterial or, less frequently, fungal illness (Barros et al. 2023). In the majority of cases, weight loss is observed, often reaching as high as 90-95%. This is a significant diagnostic symptom, since unintentional weight loss, together with anemia and an elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate, indicates the presence of inflammatory causes. Pleural effusion, pericardial effusion, lymphadenopathy, fibrosis, or cavitations on imaging are examples of severe disease symptoms. Studies suggest a higher likelihood of chronicity is associated with aberrant immunological and radiographic findings. Additional physical exam results that have been recorded include enlargement of the liver and spleen, finger or face edema, and chest and/or abdomen discomfort. The fact that 50–75% of people have breath odor similar to ammonia is also noteworthy and might be of interest (Wijaya et al. 2021).

Disseminated Pulmonary Histoplasmosis

Disseminated illness primarily affects persons who have been exposed to *H. capsulatum* and have weakened immune systems. However, a significant infection with a large amount of the pathogen can lead to serious disease in ~29% of people without immunological abnormalities. Patients with HIV/AIDS, especially those with a CD4 count below 200 cells per μl , are at a higher risk of disseminated pulmonary histoplasmosis. However, persistent steroid usage and immunosuppression due to

malignancy are also additional risk factors for the illness (Nacher et al. 2014).

Clinical presentations of disseminated histoplasmosis are nonspecific and may include "fever, anorexia, malaise, weight loss, lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly, and skin ulcers." Severe cases can lead to multiorgan failure, adrenal insufficiency, and chronic progressive disseminated histoplasmosis, particularly affecting elderly individuals with no known immunosuppression (Gandhi et al. 2021).

Pathogenesis of *Histoplasma capsulatum*

After inhalation, conidia are usually filtered out in the respiratory tract and do not cause disease. However, conidia may transform into blastospores and establish infection when tissue becomes necrotic. The trigger for this morphological conversion is not known, but cell wall changes such as an increase in α -(1-3)-glucan may signal the change to a tissue phase. α -(1-3)-glucan is not detectable in mycelial conidia, but it can be found in intracellular pigmented yeast cells. It is suggested that the change from the environmental to the tissue morphology is the critical step that enables the fungus to establish itself in tissues and cause disease. The absence of detailed information about *H. capsulatum* adhesion factors that initiate and facilitate binding to phagocytes is especially relevant in macrophage physiologic processes, where the phagocyte is involved in both neural regulation and control of iron homeostasis (Rodrigues Hoffmann et al. 2023).

There are many effectors that allow *H. capsulatum* to increase its resistance to host defense mechanisms. The surface carbohydrates α -glucans, fucose, and mannans contribute to evasion of phagocyte innate responses, nutrient depletion, and drug inhibition. Interestingly, cell wall glucans are found in their short β -1,3- but especially α -1,3-linked form in the majority of mycelial α -glucan containing fungi, whereas long β -1,3-linked glucans are an abundant-composing

factor of conidial and hyphal cell walls of the dimorphic fungi. In contrast, cell wall glucans are found predominantly in their long β -1,3-linked form in the yeast phase of dimorphic fungi (Wang et al. 2023). This suggests that cell wall β -1,3-glucan composition may be an important morphotype-specific characteristic of dimorphic fungi during association with the mammalian host. It stimulates both T-cell responses as well as hosts' alternative complement pathway, thus inferring that histoplasma might have evolved other compensatory mechanisms to avoid immune cell activation (Zhong et al. 2023).

The immune response to the inhaled spores plays an essential role in deciding the infection's fate. In individuals with a well-functioning immune system, over 95% of lung infections show no symptoms. Although, if a person is exposed to a large number of spores for a lengthy period of time, it can result in a cute and limited pulmonary infection. On the other hand, immunocompromised individuals frequently experience histoplasmosis as a disseminated disease from primary pulmonary infection (Jones et al. 2020). Understanding the pathogenesis of *H. capsulatum* is crucial for developing effective treatment and prevention strategies for pulmonary histoplasmosis, especially in the context of environmental disruptions, climate change, and heightened immunosuppressive conditions, which have resulted in alterations in the occurrence and distribution of histoplasmosis (Valdez et al. 2022).

Immune Response to *Histoplasma capsulatum*

The body is protected from microorganisms by numerous defense mechanisms that serve to block microbial growth and diminish the development of infection. The initial defense mechanisms consist of physical barriers, like the skin and mucous membranes, that avoid pathogens from entering. Once microorganisms pass through the physical barriers, they immediately come into contact with the immune system, which may be categorized into the non-specific (innate

immunity) and adaptive (acquired immunity) immune systems (Kiboneka, 2021).

Innate Immunity

The innate immune response, which occurs immediately, within hours after an *H. capsulatum* infection, activates the acquired immune system. The first cellular tissues with which the inhaled organism comes into contact are the alveoli, which consist of "alveolar type I and type II epithelial cells as well as alveolar macrophages." Alveolar macrophages are crucial in protecting the body against infections by their phagocytotic and killing activities, and release early anti-inflammatory cytokines playing regulatory roles in pulmonary inflammation, being a part of the so-called "silencing" of the immune response aimed to return to homeostasis after lung infections (Kirkland & Fierer, 2020).

After inhalation of conidia or mycelial fragments, humans become infected via the respiratory route. When the infection is not efficiently controlled by the innate or adaptive immune responses, the disease can disseminate. The development and regulation of the host's immune response to *H. capsulatum* depend on the recognition of the innate immune system. Innate immunity predicts the intensity of neutrophil recruitment and the fungal burden in the lungs of resistant mice, while genetically susceptible mice that lack this innate recognition of *H. capsulatum* display a weak pulmonary neutrophil response and have a high fungal burden. Moreover, infected IL-1 receptor knockout (KO) mice, which produce low levels of inflammatory cytokines in their lungs, exhibit decreased expression of pulmonary RNT, 21 LCN2, and p47phox in comparison to IL-1R1 KO mice (Hillion et al. 2020).

Adaptive Immunity

Adaptive immunity in response to *H. capsulatum* has been demonstrated in animal models and subjects exposed to the fungal pathogen. T and B lymphocytes play major roles in adaptive immunity. T helper type 1 (Th1) CD4+ T cells produce and respond to interferon gamma (IFN- γ), which is essentially required for antifungal defense. Phagocytic cells like

neutrophils, dendritic cells, and macrophages are also a part of Th1 immunity. After recognizing *H. capsulatum* antigens via the T cell receptor, naive T cells expand and proliferate, developing effector functions (Almeida et al. 2020). A specialized memory population develops from these rapidly dividing effector cells. Although lost in great part after the acute period of infection, memory T cells enable the host to combat secondary (frequently more intense) exposure to infections. Moreover, B lymphocytes are essential to the development of *H. capsulatum* illness. After activation, B cells secrete antibodies with a specific affinity for fungal antigens. Typically, they directly neutralize fungal mobility, toxins, or ability to

protect against phagocytosis (Sharma et al. 2022).

Inversely, fungal killing can be mediated by binding serum antibodies to *H. capsulatum* via phagocytic cell-Fc receptors (FcR) in what is termed antibody-dependent cellular phagocytosis. Thus, like for T cells and depending on the strain, B lymphocytes and antibodies can be beneficial or detrimental during different stages of *H. capsulatum* disease (Willment, 2022). In summary, both the innate and adaptive immune system responses directly or indirectly, will interplay with the gastric system to protect the host from Histoplasma and initiate the wound-healing response (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pulmonary Histoplasmosis and Its Impact on The Immune Response

Virulence Factors of *Histoplasma capsulatum*

H. capsulatum, the microorganism responsible for causing pulmonary histoplasmosis, exhibits many virulence factors that enhance its ability to cause disease. An important determinant is its ability to exist in two distinct morphological forms, it can live in the environment as a mold and in human tissues as a yeast. The transition to the yeast phase within the host, particularly

within macrophages, allows the fungus to evade immune detection and establish infection. Additionally, the infectious particles of *H. capsulatum*, namely macroconidia and microconidia, are primarily responsible for the development of illness, particularly in the lungs. These factors collectively contribute to the ability of *H. capsulatum* to cause disease and evade the immune system, highlighting the complex interplay between the pathogen and its host (Barros et al. 2023). In order to evade detection

and elimination by the innate immune response, *H. capsulatum* possesses surface molecules that facilitate its interaction with immune cells. *H. capsulatum* possibly utilizes host macrophages to provide a specialized environment for its growth and reproduction. Hence, an innate immune response alone cannot prevent infection with *H. capsulatum* (Ray & Rappleye, 2019). Furthermore, "the heat shock protein 60 (HSP60)," regulating protein folding in cells, is a substantial surface component facilitating activated macrophages' engulfment of *H. capsulatum*. It has been suggested that HSP60 from *H. capsulatum* protects the organism from antibody responses and promotes biofilm production (Fregonezi et al. 2021). As well, the cell wall of *H. capsulatum* has α -glucan, which conceals β -glucan. This β -glucan has been recognized by immune cells due to its antigenic properties. *H. capsulatum* is linked to reduced pathogenicity and a prompt immunological response when it lacks α -glucan (Qi et al. 2020). In addition, fungal hydroxamate siderophores and histones serve as pathogenic factors that contribute to the immune response's activation (Hwang et al. 2008).

Besides, a total of three antigens that are specifically identified by antibodies of individuals with histoplasmosis have been discovered as prospective targets for antigens. These include the M antigen, which has been previously used in the diagnosis of histoplasmosis, as well as the YPS-3 and catalase P proteins. These proteins are recognized as virulence factors of *H. capsulatum*, although their antigenic characteristics remain not fully understood. Two proteins remained, comprising fragments of the YPS-3 and M antigen. The two bioinformatics techniques produced overlapping findings, identifying 16 areas within these proteins as potential *H. capsulatum*-specific B-cell epitopes. This observation uncovers a novel function of these proteins in the interactions between *H. capsulatum* and the immune system, suggesting their potential use in novel diagnostic strategies for histoplasmosis (Almeida et al. 2020)

Understanding these virulence factors is a first step in developing preventive and treatment strategies for a potentially serious pulmonary

disease, particularly in the context of changing epidemiology and increased risk with immunosuppression (Adenis et al. 2014).

Pathophysiology of Pulmonary Histoplasmosis and COVID-19

Histoplasmosis and COVID-19 are classified as respiratory tract infections. Pulmonary histoplasmosis occurs following inhalation of a respiratory fungal pathogen, *H. capsulatum*. Conversely, The main cause of COVID-19 is the extremely contagious virus known as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), wherein viral infection causes the pathobiology of viral "pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)". Thus, the two infections affect overlapping areas of the lung, have similar symptoms, and can eventually lead to hypoxemia (Eibschutz et al. 2022). However, it has never examined the potential relationships between having baseline *H. capsulatum* infections within the lungs and the influence of *H. capsulatum* on COVID-19 outcomes. People, especially in North America, who are residing in the Ohio or Mississippi River Valley region or from Central or South America, may already have some degree of lung damage from previous benign, and most likely unknown, *H. capsulatum* infections. Thus, it could be hypothesized that this pre-existing, lung impairment may exacerbate lung disease/physiology in COVID-19 and lead to worsened patient outcomes (Katal et al. 2023).

There is a possibility for worse symptoms and outcomes of (SARS-CoV-2) infection from pre-existing pulmonary histoplasmosis-related lung damage. It is yet to be established whether intensifying arising lung inflammation from a previous benign *H. capsulatum* infection would have any impact on the incitement and progression of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Furthermore, potential histoplasmosis-associated tissue alteration due to abnormal fibroblast interactions and tissue fibrosis may also detriment the attaining of improved, assisted ventilator therapy (Dangarembizi et al. 2023). The majority of the cons associated with both diseases are attributed to the virus

responsible for COVID-19, which has limited understanding due to being newly identified viral strains of zoonotic origin. Antifungals would not be reliably helpful in this case, and as such, the general treatment focus in COVID-19 is towards effectively minimizing inflammation. The therapeutic interventions, unlike those for other infectious diseases, have a spectrum of side effects that can be worse than the disease itself. With impending further waves of infections from strong infective variants of SARS-CoV-2, the establishment of a nested basic clinical approach that manages these factors in the lungs of patients at medical risk, has its long-term effects mitigated as compared to other consequence options (Frutos et al. 2021).

The presence of COVID-19 may increase the susceptibility to acute pulmonary histoplasmosis due to lung inflammation and lung damage. Administering corticosteroids to individuals with severe COVID-19 might potentially cause a resurgence of pulmonary histoplasmosis. Inflammatory signaling pathways that are initiated during an infection with *H. capsulatum* may predispose individuals to worsening COVID-19, and vice versa. Additionally, individuals with COVID-19 who have low lymphocyte counts may be more susceptible to pulmonary histoplasmosis. Furthermore, the activation of inflammatory signaling pathways in response to *H. capsulatum* infection might also potentially worsen COVID-19 disease and vice versa (Almutawif et al. 2023).

Diagnostic Approaches

The diagnosis of acute pulmonary histoplasmosis is difficult because it has nonspecific clinical manifestations that often overlap with other pulmonary diseases, such as tuberculosis. Misdiagnosis may lead to delays in treatment, potentially resulting in fatal outcomes if left untreated. Accurate diagnosis of pulmonary histoplasmosis is crucial for effective management (Zhu et al. 2016).

Microbiological tests, such as culturing *H. capsulatum* from respiratory specimens, remain fundamental for definitive diagnosis, which is

typically achieved through culture on Sabouraud agar and subsequent incubation at a temperature between 25 °C and 30 °C. The development of mycelium takes place throughout a period of 2 to 3 weeks, and a definitive diagnosis often requires confirmatory tests such as matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry or chemiluminescent DNA probe, which is often necessary for accurately diagnosing *H. capsulatum*. Histopathology is the main technique used to identify *H. capsulatum* in clinical samples. It involves examining the tissue for specific characteristics, including granulomas and the presence of ovoid, narrow-based budding yeasts inside macrophages or freely in the tissue. These findings are indicative of histoplasmosis (Barros et al. 2023). As well, histological evaluation plays an important role in the diagnosis of pulmonary histoplasmosis, differentiating it from other pulmonary diseases due to the fact that it may present clinically asymptomatic, or may present symptoms that may be indistinguishable from those of other lung diseases, so a complete histological assessment is important for diagnosis, especially when the clinical presentation is atypical or uncertain (Zhu et al. 2016). In addition, cytopathology, most commonly through bronchoalveolar lavage, is another diagnostic option that has a sensitivity of 48% for acute pulmonary histoplasmosis, but sensitivity increases to 97% when used with antigen testing (Rosen, 2022). Serology is particularly advantageous in the diagnosis of chronic and subacute illnesses. Several methods include "complement fixation enzyme immunoassay, immunodiffusion, and radioimmunoassay". Although molecular procedures have not yet received FDA approval, they can nevertheless be beneficial due to their high specificity and quicker processing time (Azar & Hage, 2017).

Imaging investigations are critical for the diagnosis and evaluation of pulmonary histoplasmosis. "Chest X-rays and CT scans" are usually used to help identify unique features of pulmonary histoplasmosis. Imaging can reveal different patterns, such as focal or diffuse pulmonary nodules, mediastinal lymphadenopathy, and pulmonary infiltrates.

For example, in individuals with an intact immune system, the findings seen on imaging may be localized or solitary nodules. In comparison, an immuno-compromised host may present with diffuse miliary nodules. CT imaging can also provide specificity regarding findings such as ground glass opacities (GGO) and consolidations in patchy or geographic distribution to assist practitioners with interpretations for treatment recommendations (Zhu et al. 2016).

Treatment Strategies

There are a variety of management options for pulmonary histoplasmosis that are individualized based on disease severity and the patient's immune status. Antifungal agents play an important role in the management of pulmonary histoplasmosis. In patients with milder pulmonary histoplasmosis, the preferred treatment is itraconazole. In the case of severe or refractory disease, particularly in the immunosuppressed host, it is preferable to use liposomal amphotericin B as it offers improved treatment outcomes. Supportive care and symptom management (fever, chills, cough), can all be considered helpful adjuncts to treatment. It is important to recognize that, in addition to anti-fungal therapy, patients who are HIV positive should also be on effective antiretroviral therapy (ART), since this will not only decrease the risk of developing histoplasmosis, but will also provide a greater treatment response (McKinsey, 2021).

In the management of complications and severe cases of pulmonary histoplasmosis, surgical intervention is essential. In some circumstances, if antifungal therapy is inadequate, surgical intervention is necessary to either treat complications such as fibrosing mediastinitis or to resect specific lung lesions (Hevroni et al. 2018).

Conclusion

In patients with concurrent immunocompromising conditions, the risk for

pulmonary histoplasmosis is potentially life-threatening. Therefore, it is essential to recognize the disease early and accurately. The morbidity and mortality associated with histoplasmosis are low in immunocompetent hosts. On the other hand, the environmental disruption of habitats with large quantities of bird or bat fecal matter is a significant factor associated with sporadic, localized outbreaks of histoplasmosis. Early and accurate diagnosis, followed by suitable treatment, is essential in avoiding the development of pulmonary histoplasmosis and minimizing associated morbidity and mortality.

References

- Adenis, A.A., Aznar, C., & Couppié, P. (2014). Histoplasmosis in HIV-Infected Patients: A Review of New Developments and Remaining Gaps. *Curr Trop Med Rep*, 1(2),119-128. <https://doi:10.1007/s40475-014-0017-8>
- Almeida, M.A., Almeida-Paes, R., Guimarães, A.J., Valente, R.H., Soares, C.M.A., & Zancopé-Oliveira, R.M. (2020). Immunoproteomics Reveals Pathogen's Antigens Involved in Homo sapiens-Histoplasma capsulatum Interaction and Specific Linear B-Cell Epitopes in Histoplasmosis. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*, 10,591121. <https://doi:10.3389/fcimb.2020.591121>
- Almutawif, Y.A., Kurashy, H.M., Al-Gareeb, A.I., Alexiou, A., Papadakis, M., Eid, H.M.A., Saad, H.M., & Batiha, G.E. (2023). Insights on Covid-19 with superimposed pulmonary histoplasmosis: The possible nexus. *Immun Inflamm Dis*, 11(9),e989. <https://doi:10.1002/iid3.989>
- Azar, M.M., & Hage, C.A. (2017). Laboratory Diagnostics for Histoplasmosis. *J Clin Microbiol*, 55(6),1612-1620. <https://doi:10.1128/JCM.02430-16>
- Bagal, U.R., Gade, L., Benedict, K., Howell, V., Christophe, N., Gibbons-Burgener, S., Hallyburton, S., Ireland, M., McCracken, S., Metobo, A.K., Signs, K., Warren, K.A., Litvintseva, A.P., & Chow, N.A. (2023). A

Phylogeographic Description of *Histoplasma capsulatum* in the United States. *J Fungi (Basel)*, 9(9),884. <https://doi:10.3390/jof9090884>

Bagal, U.R., Gade, L., Benedict, K., Howell, V., Christophe, N., Gibbons-Burgener, S., Hallyburton, S., Ireland, M., McCracken, S., Metobo, A.K., Signs, K., Warren, K.A., Litvintseva, A.P., & Chow, N.A. (2023). A Phylogeographic Description of *Histoplasma capsulatum* in the United States. *J Fungi (Basel)*, 9(9),884. <https://doi:10.3390/jof9090884>

Barros, N., Wheat, J.L., & Hage, C. (2023). Pulmonary Histoplasmosis: A Clinical Update. *J Fungi (Basel)*, 9(2),236. <https://doi:10.3390/jof9020236>

Brilhante, R.S.N., Costa, A.d.C., Mesquita, J.R.L.d, dos Santos Araújo, G., Freire, R.S., Nunes, J.V.S., Nobre, A.F.D., Fernandes, M.R., Rocha, M.F.G., & Pereira Neto, W.d.A., et al. (2023). Antifungal Activity of Chitosan against *Histoplasma capsulatum* in Planktonic and Biofilm Forms: A Therapeutic Strategy in the Future? *Journal of Fungi*, 9(12), 1201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9121201>

Chen, Q., Guo, W., Guo, W., Mu, X., & Guo, J. (2024). Pulmonary histoplasmosis on the Chinese mainland: two case reports and literature review. *J Infect Dev Ctries*, 18(2),318-325. <https://doi:10.3855/jidc.17934>

Dangarembizi, R., Wasserman, S., & Hoving, J.C. (2023). Emerging and re-emerging fungal threats in Africa. *Parasite Immunol*, 45(2),e12953. <https://doi:10.1111/pim.12953>

Eibschutz, L.S., Rabiee, B., Asadollahi, S., Gupta, A., Assadi, M., Alavi, A., & Gholamrezanezhad, A. (2022). FDG-PET/CT of COVID-19 and Other Lung Infections. *Semin Nucl Med*, 52(1),61-70. <https://doi:10.1053/j.semnuclmed.2021.06.017>

Fregonezi, N.F., Oliveira, L.T., Singulani, J.L., Marcos, C.M., Dos Santos, C.T., Taylor, M.L., Mendes-Giannini, M.J.S., de Oliveira, H.C., & Fusco-Almeida, A.M. (2021). Heat Shock Protein 60, Insights to Its Importance in *Histoplasma capsulatum*: From Biofilm Formation to Host-Interaction. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*,

10,591950.

<https://doi:10.3389/fcimb.2020.591950>

Frutos, R., Gavotte, L., & Devaux, C.A. (2021). Understanding the origin of COVID-19 requires to change the paradigm on zoonotic emergence from the spillover to the circulation model. *Infect Genet Evol*, 95,104812. <https://doi:10.1016/j.meegid.2021.104812>

Gandhi, D., Gandhi, T., Wolfe, A., Kichloo, A., Singh, J., Batts, K.P., & Patel, L. (2021). Disseminated histoplasmosis leading to end stage liver failure in immunocompetent patient: case report and review of literature. *Radiol Case Rep*, 16(8),2214-2219. <https://doi:10.1016/j.radcr.2021.05.010>

Hevroni, A., Springer, C., Wasser, O., Avital, A., & Koplewitz, B.Z. (2018). Recurrent Pneumonia due to Fibrosing Mediastinitis in a Teenage Girl: A Case Report with Long-Term Follow-Up. *Case Rep Pediatr*, 2018,3246929. <https://doi:10.1155/2018/3246929>

Hillion, S., Arleevskaya, M.I., Blanco, P., Bordron, A., Brooks, W.H., Cesbron, J.Y., Kaveri, S., Vivier, E., & Renaudineau, Y. (2020). The Innate Part of the Adaptive Immune System. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol*, 58(2),151-154. <https://doi:10.1007/s12016-019-08740-1>

Hwang, L.H., Mayfield, J.A., Rine, J., & Sil, A. (2008). Histoplasma requires SID1, a member of an iron-regulated siderophore gene cluster, for host colonization. *PLoS Pathog*, 4(4),e1000044. <https://doi:10.1371/journal.ppat.1000044>

Jones, G.S., Sepúlveda, V.E., & Goldman, W.E. (2020). Biodiverse Histoplasma Species Elicit Distinct Patterns of Pulmonary Inflammation following Sublethal Infection. *mSphere*, 5(4),e00742-20. <https://doi:10.1128/mSphere.00742-20>.

Katal, S., Eibschutz, L.S., Gupta, A., Johnston, S.K., Flors, L., & Gholamrezanezhad, A. (2023). Co-infections and Secondary Infections in COVID-19 Pneumonia. *Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). A Clinical Guide*, Chapter 14,319-338. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119789741.ch14>

- Kiboneka, A. (2021). Principals of innate and adaptive immunity. Immunity to microbes & fundamental concepts in immunology. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 10(03),188-197. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2021.10.3.0271>
- Kirkland, T.N., & Fierer, J. (2020). Innate Immune Receptors and Defense Against Primary Pathogenic Fungi. *Vaccines (Basel)*, 8(2),303. <https://doi:10.3390/vaccines8020303>
- Lockhart, S.R., Toda, M., Benedict, K., Caceres, D.H., & Litvintseva, A.P. (2021). Endemic and Other Dimorphic Mycoses in The Americas. *J Fungi (Basel)*, 7(2),151. <https://doi:10.3390/jof7020151>
- McKinsey, D.S. (2021). Treatment and Prevention of Histoplasmosis in Adults Living with HIV. *J Fungi (Basel)*, 7(6),429. <https://doi:10.3390/jof7060429>
- Nacher, M., Adenis, A., Blanchet, D., Vantilcke, V., Demar, M., Basurko, C., Gaubert-Maréchal, E., Dufour, J., Aznar, C., Carme, B., & Couppié, P. (2014). Risk factors for disseminated histoplasmosis in a cohort of HIV-infected patients in French Guiana. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 8(1),e2638. <https://doi:10.1371/journal.pntd.0002638>
- Qi, C.Y., Jia, S.L., Wei, X., Yang, G., Chi, Z., Liu, G.L., Hu, Z., & Chi, Z.M. (2020). The differences between fungal α -glucan synthase determining pullulan synthesis and that controlling cell wall α -1,3 glucan synthesis. *Int J Biol Macromol*, 162,436-444. <https://doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.06.147>
- Ray, S.C., & Rappleye, C.A. (2019). Flying under the radar: *Histoplasma capsulatum* avoidance of innate immune recognition. *Semin Cell Dev Biol*, 89,91-98. <https://doi:10.1016/j.semcdb.2018.03.009>
- Rodrigues Hoffmann, A., Ramos, M.G., Walker, R.T., & Stranahan, L.W. (2023). Hyphae, pseudohyphae, yeasts, spherules, spores, and more: A review on the morphology and pathology of fungal and oomycete infections in the skin of domestic animals. *Vet Pathol*, 60(6),812-828. <https://doi:10.1177/03009858231173715>
- Rosen, Y. (2022). Pathology of Granulomatous Pulmonary Diseases. *Arch Pathol Lab Med*, 146(2),233-251. <https://doi:10.5858/arpa.2020-0543-RA>
- Sayeed, M., Benzamin, M., Nahar, L., Rana, M., & Aishy, A.S. (2022). Hepatic Histoplasmosis: An Update. *J Clin Transl Hepatol*, 10(4),726-729. <https://doi:10.14218/JCTH.2020.00080>
- Sharma, J., Mudalagiriappa, S., & Nanjappa, S.G. (2022). T cell responses to control fungal infection in an immunological memory lens. *Front Immunol*, 13,905867. <https://doi:10.3389/fimmu.2022.905867>
- Souza, D.C., Rodrigues-Neto, A.A., Monnerat, G.M.B., Sardou, M., Hottz, P.L., Oliveira, J., McBenedict, B., Vilte, R.M.C.V., Fonseca, S.C., & Martins, E.B. (2023). Acute pulmonary histoplasmosis: a case series from an outbreak in Southeastern Brazil. *Rev Inst Med Trop Sao Paulo*,65,e45. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1678-9946202365045>
- Sun, Z., Zhang, N., Li, Y., & Xu, X. (2020). A systematic review of chest imaging findings in COVID-19. *Quant Imaging Med Surg*, 10(5),1058-1079. <https://doi:10.21037/qims-20-564>
- Taylor, M.L., Reyes-Montes, M.D.R., Estrada-Bárceñas, D.A., Zancopé-Oliveira, R.M., Rodríguez-Arellanes, G., & Ramírez, J.A. (2022). Considerations about the Geographic Distribution of *Histoplasma* Species. *Appl Environ Microbiol*, 88(7),e0201021. <https://doi:10.1128/aem.02010-21>
- Valdez, A.F., Miranda, D.Z., Guimarães, A.J., Nimrichter, L., & Nosanchuk, J.D. (2022). Pathogenicity & virulence of *Histoplasma capsulatum* - A multifaceted organism adapted to intracellular environments. *Virulence*, 13(1),1900-1919. <https://doi:10.1080/21505594.2022.2137987>
- Wang, H., Lu, Z., Keyhani, N.O., Deng, J., Zhao, X., Huang, S., Luo, Z., Jin, K., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Insect fungal pathogens secrete a cell wall-associated glucanase that acts to help avoid recognition by the host immune system. *PLoS Pathog*, 19(8),e1011578. <https://doi:10.1371/journal.ppat.1011578>

Wheat, L.J., Azar, M.M., Bahr, N.C., Spec, A., Relich, R.F., & Hage C. (2016). Histoplasmosis. *Infect Dis Clin North Am*, 30(1),207-227. <https://doi:10.1016/j.idc.2015.10.009>

Wijaya, M., Adawiyah, R., & Wahyuningsih, R. (2021). Histoplasmosis: Diagnostic and therapeutic aspect. *Indonesian Journal of Tropical and Infectious Disease*, 9(2),66-78. <https://doi.org/10.20473/ijtid.v9i2.25448>

Willment, J.A. (2022). Fc-conjugated C-type lectin receptors: Tools for understanding host-pathogen interactions. *Mol Microbiol*, 117(3),632-660. <https://doi:10.1111/mmi.14837>

Zhong, X., Wang, G., Li, F., Fang, S., Zhou, S., Ishiwata, A., Tonevitsky, A.G., Shkurnikov, M., Cai, H., & Ding, F. (2023). Immunomodulatory Effect and Biological Significance of β -Glucans. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(6),1615. <https://doi:10.3390/pharmaceutics15061615>

Zhu, C., Wang, G., Chen, Q., He, B., & Wang, L. (2016). Pulmonary histoplasmosis in a immunocompetent patient: A case report and literature review. *Exp Ther Med*, 12(5),3256-3260. <https://doi:10.3892/etm.2016.3774>